

Safe-guarding pea and field bean growth and yield: quantifying rhizobia in field soils

Problem

Poor growth and so yield of pulse crops such as pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) and field bean (*Vicia faba* L.) due to low levels of root nodulation as a function of low rhizobia numbers in soil.

Solution

Application of a molecular diagnostic method can quantify the number of pea- and bean-rhizobia in soil; with low population numbers indicating a limitation to crop performance and yield.

Benefits

With the number of rhizobia in-soil known, this potentially yield-limiting factor can be identified or excluded. If rhizobia numbers are low, high-performing (elite) rhizobia from commercial sources should be applied to seed before sowing.

Applicability box

Theme

Pulse crop performance and yield protection.

Keywords

Crop growth; yield; rhizobia; molecular diagnostics; elite rhizobia.

Context

Wherever peas and beans are grown in-field.

Required time

Molecular Diagnostics: allow 2 months.
Elite rhizobia application: allow 2 weeks (for delivery); seed inoculation is rapid (1-2h)

Period of impact

Within 4 weeks improved root nodulation and seedling growth should be apparent.

Specialist Equipment: Not necessary on farm.

Best in: any cropped system type.

Practical recommendation

- Molecular diagnostics demands specific equipment, and expertise, and need carried out by professional service providers including: the Processors and Growers Research Organisation (Roger Vickers; roger@pgro.org); and/or the James Hutton Institute (pete.iannetta@hutton.ac.uk).
- If rhizobia numbers are low a relatively low-cost remedy (even without the molecular diagnostic test), is the application of high performing ('elite') rhizobia to seed before sowing.

- Elite rhizobia should be purchased from high quality commercial providers e.g., Legume Technology Ltd, www.legumetechnology.co.uk.

An illustrative graph showing the potential relationship between bean yield and abundance of soil rhizobia. Noting low yield is not always due to low rhizobia numbers, as other factors may be important too.

Further Reading

Maluk et al., (2021). Fields with no recent legume cultivation have sufficient nitrogen-fixing rhizobia for crops of faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.). *Plant and Soil*, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11104-021-05246-8>.

Macdonald et al., (2011). Development of a real-time PCR assay for detection and quantification of *Rhizobium leguminosarum* bacteria and discrimination between different biovars in zinc-contaminated soil. *Applied and environmental microbiology* **77**, 4626-4633. <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.02232-10>.

About this practice abstracts

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